

Flow cessation and topology of static plugs in viscoplastic flow through curved ducts

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of curvature on the topology and morphology of static plug regions arising at the cessation threshold of viscoplastic flow. By invoking the conservation of angular momentum, a general criterion for the existence of plug regions in curved ducts with arbitrary cross-sections is established. The parametric method is adopted to derive an exact representation of the static plug topology in the curved ducts. Plug configurations and critical Bingham numbers are computed using a simulated annealing algorithm and are validated against three-dimensional numerical simulations and available literature results. The variational formulation shows that a curvature-weighted perimeter-to-area ratio governs the critical condition, linking to weighted Cheeger problems and enabling a unified geometric criterion for identifying plug-free conditions based on duct curvature and cross-sectional geometry.

The analysis is carried out for circular, elliptical, and rectangular geometries over a wide range of aspect and curvature ratios. The results identify plug-free regimes in curved elliptical ducts and show that static plugs persist in circular geometries for curvature ratios exceeding 0.382. Regime maps describing plug topology are also constructed, and the boundary of the plug-free regime in the aspect ratio–curvature ratio space is determined analytically for curved elliptical ducts. Despite the complex functional dependence of the exact plug boundaries, they are accurately approximated by elliptical shapes, with errors below 2%. Static plug-free geometries, designed using the proposed curvature-based criteria, can reduce stagnant regions and thrombus formation in curved vessels such as varicose veins, with potential applications in developing low-occlusion vascular grafts.

Keywords: Viscoplastic Fluid; Curved Duct; Conservation of Angular Momentum; Critical Condition; Topology of Static Plugs.

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1. Introduction

The flow of viscoplastic fluids is characterized by the existence of a finite yield stress below which the material behaves as a rigid solid. As a result, the flow domain generally partitions into yielded and unyielded regions, with the latter forming rigid plugs whose shape and extent are not known *a priori* but must be determined as part of the solution. This gives rise to a nonlinear free-boundary problem, in which the global stress field governs the location and topology of the yield surfaces and may undergo qualitative changes with variations in geometry or forcing. These challenges are further amplified in curved ducts, where curvature induces non-uniform stress distributions and breaks the symmetry present in straight geometries. Such configurations arise in a wide range of applications, including the transport of slurries and drilling fluids, food and personal care processing, and other industrial systems involving complex conduit geometries. In these settings, curvature can significantly alter not only the size but also the connectivity of unyielded regions, leading to asymmetric or multiple disconnected static plugs.

A rigorous theoretical framework for such problems originates from variational formulations of viscoplastic flow. Early contributions by Prager (1954) and Yoshioka & Adachi (1971, 1973) introduced extremum principles based on virtual work and stress optimization, providing a foundation for identifying admissible velocity and stress fields in yield-stress materials. These ideas were subsequently formalized by Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966), who employed variational principles to derive conditions for flow in channels at large Bingham numbers and to establish criteria for the existence of stagnant regions. In particular, their results enable the identification of critical conditions under which the central plug extends to form fully unyielded states in ducts. This approach was later developed and extended by Huilgol (2006) and Huilgol and Georgiou (2021), who demonstrated that steady duct flows of Bingham-type fluids can be formulated as variational inequalities, with yield surfaces emerging naturally as free boundaries. Within this framework, explicit criteria for the existence of dead regions and the determination of the minimum pressure gradient required for flow initiation can be obtained. These results provide a unified basis for analyzing plug formation and critical conditions in ducts of arbitrary cross-section.

Within this variational perspective, the structure of unyielded regions in straight ducts has been extensively characterized. In simple geometries such as circular pipes and planar channels, the plug typically occupies the core region, and its size can be determined from stress-balance arguments. In contrast, in non-circular ducts, such as rectangular channels, the stress distribution becomes highly non-uniform, leading to the formation of additional unyielded regions near corners where the shear rate vanishes. As a result, the plug topology may include multiple disconnected regions, whose shape and extent depend on geometric parameters such as the aspect ratio and the imposed pressure gradient (Huilgol 2006; Mitsoulis & Tsamopoulos 2017).

In this context, several analytical and semi-analytical techniques have been proposed to improve the prediction of plug regions in non-circular geometries. Among these, recent developments have introduced alternative mathematical frameworks for analyzing viscoplastic flows in rectangular ducts, enabling more direct identification of unyielded regions and improved estimation of critical conditions (Norouzi *et al.* 2021). Such approaches complement classical variational formulations by providing more explicit representations of plug boundaries, particularly in geometries where corner singularities and stress localization complicate traditional analyses.

Complementary to these analytical developments, extensive numerical work has been devoted to the detection and characterization of plug regions in straight geometries. Regularization techniques and augmented Lagrangian methods have emerged as the two dominant computational approaches for resolving yield surfaces. Finite element and finite difference simulations have provided detailed predictions of velocity fields, plug shapes, and critical Bingham numbers in ducts of various cross-sections (Taylor & Wilson 1997; Saramito & Roquet 2001; Moyers-Gonzalez & Frigaard 2004). In particular, Moyers-Gonzalez & Frigaard (2004) directly compared regularization and augmented Lagrangian approaches in duct flows of viscoplastic fluids, demonstrating that accurate identification of unyielded regions is intrinsically linked to the numerical formulation of the problem rather than being a purely post-processing task.

This observation is closely related to the broader body of work by Frigaard and co-workers, which has emphasized the interplay between geometry, constitutive modeling, and the mathematical structure of yield surfaces. The review by Frigaard & Nouar (2005) demonstrated that regularization techniques must be applied with care, as the convergence to the ideal viscoplastic

solution may influence the predicted extent and topology of unyielded regions. In subsequent studies, Frigaard & Ryan (2004) analyzed viscoplastic flow in channels of slowly varying width, while Balmforth *et al.* (2014) examined yield surfaces, critical yield conditions, and flow cessation in a range of configurations. A key outcome of these works is that plug topology is not merely a geometric consequence, but a manifestation of how the stress field reorganizes itself under constraints imposed by geometry and boundary conditions. This perspective is particularly relevant in the presence of curvature, where stress redistribution is inherently asymmetric and may induce qualitative changes in plug connectivity and topology.

In parallel, detailed numerical investigations by Mitsoulis, Tsamopoulos, and their collaborators have further clarified the structure and evolution of unyielded regions in straight ducts. Their studies, based on both viscoplastic and elastoviscoplastic formulations, have systematically examined flows in square and rectangular ducts, highlighting the role of geometric confinement, aspect ratio, and boundary conditions on the emergence and evolution of plug regions (Mitsoulis & Tsamopoulos, 2017). More recent contributions from this group, including studies on minimum-pressure-gradient problems and geometric interpretations of critical states (e.g., Georgiou & Huilgol 2023), reinforce the idea that flow cessation in Bingham-type fluids can be linked to intrinsic geometric properties of the domain.

Taken together, these studies provide a coherent picture of plug formation and critical conditions in straight ducts. However, these results do not directly extend to curved geometries, where curvature fundamentally alters the stress field and breaks the symmetry assumptions underlying many existing analyses. Curvature fundamentally modifies the stress field, leading to asymmetric distributions that may induce qualitative changes in the topology and connectivity of unyielded regions. Existing investigations of viscoplastic flow in curved ducts have confirmed that curvature affects both the onset of flow and the distribution of yielded and unyielded regions, but have largely focused on velocity fields, flux reduction, and critical conditions rather than on detailed plug topology (Norouzi *et al.* 2015; Roberts & Cox 2020; Moyers-Gonzalez & Frigaard 2020).

From the standpoint of the present work, the studies of Roberts & Cox (2020) and Roberts & Cox (2023) are particularly relevant. Roberts & Cox (2020) derived an analytical solution for pressure-driven Bingham flow in a curved channel, demonstrating how curvature modifies the minimum

pressure gradient, the plug width, and the volumetric flux. In their subsequent work, Roberts & Cox (2023) examined viscoplastic flow in serpentine geometries, showing that curvature and geometric variation can significantly alter the size and location of unyielded regions. These studies establish curvature as an active mechanism in shaping plug structure, but do not provide a systematic characterization of plug topology across different cross-sectional geometries. Similarly, Moyers-Gonzalez & Frigaard (2020) investigated Dean flow of a Bingham fluid in a curved rectangular duct and determined the corresponding critical Bingham number using an augmented Lagrangian approach. They assumed that the shape of the static plug is an elliptical arc. Their results confirmed that curvature modifies the critical conditions for flow cessation in a non-trivial manner. Recently, Cox and Taghavi (2026) analytically and numerically investigated the pressure-driven flow of a Bingham fluid in curved channels with Navier slip at the walls, motivated by foam sclerotherapy for varicose veins. They showed that in curved channels, increasing slip length shifts the unyielded plug toward the inner wall and slightly reduces its width, unlike in straight channels, where slip does not affect plug size. Their results indicate that slip enhances yielding in regions of high curvature, which may help prevent the formation of static foam zones but could reduce the plug's effectiveness at displacing blood.

Despite these advances, a systematic characterization of the topology and connectivity of static plugs in curved ducts, particularly across different cross-sectional geometries and at the cessation threshold, remains largely unexplored. In particular, a general framework that combines variational existence criteria with a systematic characterization of plug topology in curved geometries is still lacking. The influence of curvature on the connectivity, bifurcation, and merging of static plugs across different cross-sectional shapes remains poorly understood. Furthermore, although numerical methods provide valuable insights, exact or semi-analytical descriptions of plug morphology remain scarce, especially for arbitrary geometries. The gap is therefore not simply the absence of additional simulations, but the absence of a unified framework linking criticality, geometry, and topology at the cessation threshold.

The present study addresses these issues by examining the influence of curvature on the topology and morphology of static plugs at the cessation threshold of viscoplastic flow. By invoking the law of conservation of angular momentum, a general existence criterion for static plugs in curved geometries with arbitrary cross-sections is established. An exact parametric formulation is then

derived to characterize plug topology within a nonlinear programming framework. It is further recast in a variational setting, where the critical condition is associated with a curvature-weighted perimeter-to-area ratio. This formulation provides an explicit, geometry-dependent description of plug topology and its transitions. In addition, plug-free regions are identified analytically. The analysis also seeks to identify optimized cross-sectional geometries for plug-free conditions and to develop simplified approximations for plug shapes, in addition to their exact representations. In contrast to existing approaches that primarily rely on numerical detection of yield surfaces, the present framework offers a systematic analytical description of stagnant regions. The analysis is carried out for circular, elliptical, and rectangular cross-sections over a wide range of aspect ratios and curvature ratios. Plug configurations and critical Bingham numbers are determined using a simulated annealing approach and are validated against complementary numerical simulations.

The schematic configuration of the problem is shown in Figure 1. Here, $2\tilde{a}$ and $2\tilde{b}$ denote the duct dimensions along the curvature and transverse directions, respectively. Accordingly, $2\tilde{a}$ and $2\tilde{b}$ represent the major/minor axes for elliptical ducts and the side lengths for rectangular ducts. The radius of curvature is specified by \tilde{R} .

Figure 1. Schematic of a curved duct illustrating its geometry and cross-section.

2. Governing Equations

The governing equations for flow in conduits are the conservation of mass and momentum, given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{V}} &= 0 \\ \rho \frac{D\tilde{\mathbf{V}}}{Dt} &= -\nabla \tilde{p} + \nabla \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$ is the velocity vector, \tilde{t} is time, ρ is density, \tilde{p} is pressure, and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}$ is the stress tensor. In the creeping flow regime within curved ducts, the momentum equation in cylindrical coordinates simplifies to:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\tau}_{r\theta}}{\partial \tilde{r}} + \frac{2}{\tilde{r}} \tilde{\tau}_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\tau}_{\theta z}}{\partial \tilde{z}} = \frac{1}{\tilde{r}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} \quad (3)$$

For fully developed flows, the value of $d\tilde{p}/d\theta$ is negative and constant. The stress tensor should be determined using a constitutive equation. For the case of Bingham plastics, as an example, it can be written as (Denn and Bonn 2008):

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}} = \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tilde{\gamma}_{Gen}} + \eta \right) \tilde{\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}} & \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \Pi_{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}}} > \tau_0 \\ \tilde{\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}} = 0 & \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \Pi_{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}}} \leq \tau_0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\Pi_{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}}$ is the second invariant of the stress tensor, τ_0 is the yield stress, η is the plastic viscosity, and $\tilde{\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}}$ is the shear rate tensor ($\tilde{\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}} = \nabla \tilde{\mathbf{V}} + \nabla \tilde{\mathbf{V}}^T$). In Eq. (4), $\tilde{\gamma}_{Gen}$ is the generalized shear rate and is defined based on the second invariant of the shear rate tensor as:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{Gen} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \Pi_{\tilde{\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}}}} \quad (5)$$

Assuming a rectilinear flow distribution in a cylindrical coordinate system, the shear rate tensor and the generalized shear rate are simplified as follows:

$$\tilde{\gamma} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{r}} - \frac{\tilde{v}_\theta}{\tilde{r}} & \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{z}} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{r}} - \frac{\tilde{v}_\theta}{\tilde{r}} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{z}} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6a)$$

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{Gen} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{r}} - \frac{\tilde{v}_\theta}{\tilde{r}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{z}}\right)^2} \quad (6b)$$

where \tilde{v}_θ is the axial component of the velocity vector (velocity in θ -direction). Here, the following dimensionless groups are used to nondimensionalize the parameters involved in this study:

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= \frac{\tilde{x}_i}{\tilde{a}} & L &= \frac{\tilde{b}}{\tilde{a}} & \kappa &= \frac{\tilde{a}}{\tilde{R}} & v_\theta &= \frac{\tilde{v}_\theta}{\tilde{W}_0} \\ \dot{\gamma} &= \tilde{\gamma} \frac{\tilde{a}}{\tilde{W}_0} & \tau &= \frac{\tilde{d}_h \tilde{\tau}}{\eta \tilde{W}_0} & p &= \frac{\tilde{d}_h \tilde{p}}{\eta \tilde{W}_0} & \text{Bi} &= \frac{\tau_0 \tilde{d}_h}{\eta \tilde{W}_0} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where L is the aspect ratio, κ is the curvature ratio, d_h is the hydraulic diameter, Bi is the Bingham number (the ratio of yield stress to viscous stress), and W_0 is the reference velocity, which is defined as the maximum value of velocity of a Newtonian fluid in a straight circular pipe with an identical hydraulic diameter under the same pressure gradient (White 1991):

$$\tilde{W}_0 = -\frac{\tilde{d}_h^2}{16\eta} \frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} \quad (8)$$

The hydraulic diameter is defined as $\tilde{d}_h = 4\tilde{A}_c / \tilde{\Gamma}_c$ in which \tilde{A}_c and $\tilde{\Gamma}_c$ are the area and perimeter of the cross-section. Note that no exact expression exists for the perimeter of an ellipse; for this geometry, we employ the approximation proposed by Ramanujan (Berndt 1998):

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_c = \pi \left[3(\tilde{a} + \tilde{b}) - \sqrt{(3\tilde{a} + \tilde{b})(\tilde{a} + 3\tilde{b})} \right] \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the hydraulic diameter can be defined as:

$$\text{For a rectangular duct:} \quad \tilde{d}_h = \frac{2\tilde{a}\tilde{b}}{\tilde{a} + \tilde{b}} \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{For an elliptical duct:} \quad \tilde{d}_h = \frac{4\tilde{a}\tilde{b}}{3(\tilde{a} + \tilde{b}) - \sqrt{(3\tilde{a} + \tilde{b})(\tilde{a} + 3\tilde{b})}} \quad (10b)$$

Using (2), (3), (7), and (10), the governing equations may be written in dimensionless form as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{2}{r} \tau_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \tilde{z}} + \frac{4c}{\kappa L r} = 0 \quad (11a)$$

$$\begin{cases} \tau = Bi \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}_G} + \frac{4L}{c} \dot{\gamma} & \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \Pi_\tau} > Bi \\ \dot{\gamma} = 0 & \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \Pi_\tau} \leq Bi \end{cases} \quad (11b)$$

where c is a dimensionless constant determined by the geometry of the cross-section:

$$\text{For a rectangular duct:} \quad c = 1 + L \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{For an elliptical duct:} \quad c = 3(1 + L) - \sqrt{(3 + L)(1 + 3L)} \quad (12b)$$

3. A Criterion for the Existence of Static Plugs

Earlier work by Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966 and 1967) showed that a force balance between the wall shear stress and the pressure drop yields a criterion for the existence of static plugs in straight channels. Further details of this criterion may be found in the work of Huilgol and Georgiou

(2021). In their formulation, a parameter \tilde{K} was introduced as the ratio of the yield stress to the pressure gradient in straight ducts. An analogous parameter for curved ducts may be defined as:

$$\tilde{K} = \frac{\tau_0}{\frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{P}}{d\theta}} \quad (13)$$

Based on the definition of the Bingham number in Eq. (1) and the reference velocity in Eq. (7), the Bingham number may now be represented as a function of \tilde{K} and \tilde{d}_h as follows:

$$\text{Bi} = \frac{\tau_0 \tilde{d}_h}{\eta \tilde{W}_0} = \frac{\tau_0 \tilde{d}_h}{\eta} \frac{1}{\frac{-\tilde{d}_h^2}{16\eta} \frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta}} = 16 \frac{\tau_0}{\frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta}} \frac{1}{\tilde{d}_h} \rightarrow \text{Bi} = 16 \frac{\tilde{K}}{\tilde{d}_h} \quad (14)$$

For flow in curved conduits, the analysis of Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966 and 1967) may be extended by invoking conservation of angular momentum rather than a force balance.

3.1. Lemma. Static plugs necessarily exist in viscoplastic flow through curved conduits of arbitrary cross-section if:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} < \text{Bi} < \text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}} \quad \& \quad \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 16 \frac{\tilde{R}}{d_h} \frac{\int_{A_c} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{r}_c} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \quad (15)$$

where Bi_{Cr} and Bi_{Ex} denote the critical Bingham number and the corresponding Bingham number for the existence of static plugs, respectively.

Proof. The minimum shear stress below which a viscoplastic fluid behaves as a rigid solid is given by the yield stress. Assuming that the wall shear stress equals the yield stress along the entire perimeter of the duct, a balance of angular momentum over the cross-section yields:

$$\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tau_0 \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c = - \int_{\tilde{A}_c} \tilde{r} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} d\tilde{A}_c \quad (16)$$

where \tilde{r} is the local radius of curvature, and $\tilde{\Gamma}_c$ and \tilde{A}_c are the perimeter and area of the duct cross-section, respectively. Factoring out the pressure gradient along the pitch from the right-hand side of (16) gives:

$$\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tau_0 \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c = - \frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} \int_{\tilde{A}_c} \tilde{R} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c \rightarrow \tilde{K}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{\tau_0}{-\frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta}} = \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_c} \tilde{R} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \quad (17a)$$

where \tilde{K}_{Ex} is the value of K corresponding to the existence of static plugs. In the limit of straight ducts, \tilde{R} and \tilde{r} coincide, and (17a) reduces to:

$$\tilde{K}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_c} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} = \frac{\tilde{A}_c}{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \quad (17b)$$

Equation (17b) is identical to the condition reported in Mosolov and Miasnikov (1966, 1967) for straight ducts. From (13) and (17a), the corresponding Bingham number may be written as:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{16\tilde{K}_{\text{Ex}}}{\tilde{d}_h} \rightarrow \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 16 \frac{\tilde{R}}{\tilde{d}_h} \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_c} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \quad (18)$$

Equation (17a) is derived under the condition that the wall shear stress is equal to the yield stress, such that the fluid is at the threshold of yielding at the wall. Therefore, for a given yield stress, if the pressure gradient is sufficiently small, i.e. $\tilde{K} > \tilde{K}_{\text{Ex}}$ (or $\text{Bi} > \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}}$), static plugs necessarily exist at the wall, thereby establishing the lemma. This lemma will be used later (see §4.3) to support the existence of dead regions, for example, in Dean flows. For other conditions, it follows that:

- For $\text{Bi} < \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}}$, no definitive statement can be made regarding the existence of static plugs. In such cases, certain regions along the wall—particularly near sharp corners—may experience low shear stresses and remain unyielded, while other regions may be subjected to sufficiently large shear stresses to induce yielding.
- If $\text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}} = \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}}$, no static plug forms at the wall, since the wall shear stress remains above the yield stress up to the critical condition. This situation arises, for example, in straight circular pipes.

3.2. Static Plugs in Curved Elliptical Ducts

Using (10b) and (18), a criterion for the existence of static plugs in curved elliptical ducts may be obtained as follows:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 16 \frac{\tilde{R}}{\tilde{d}_h} \frac{\int_{A_c} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \rightarrow \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{12(1+L) - 4\sqrt{(3+L)(1+3L)}}{\lambda\kappa} \frac{\int_{A_c} r dA_c}{\int_{\Gamma_c} r^2 d\Gamma_c} \quad (19)$$

Note that the parameters on the right-hand side of equation (19) are expressed in dimensionless form. Since $d\Gamma_c^2 = dx^2 + dy^2$, it follows, after rearrangement, that $d\Gamma_c = dx\sqrt{1 + (y')^2}$, where $y' = \frac{dy}{dx}$. Therefore, equation (19) can be rewritten as:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{12(1+L) - 4\sqrt{(3+L)(1+3L)}}{L\kappa} \frac{\int_{-1}^1 (\kappa^{-1} + x)y dx}{\int_{-1}^1 (\kappa^{-1} + x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} dx} \quad (20)$$

The wall geometry is defined as follows (only the upper half is shown due to symmetry about the line $y = 0$):

$$\frac{\tilde{x}^2}{\tilde{a}^2} + \frac{\tilde{y}^2}{\tilde{b}^2} = 1 \rightarrow x^2 + \frac{y^2}{L^2} = 1 \rightarrow y = L\sqrt{1 - x^2} \quad (21)$$

The integral in the numerator of equation (20) evaluates to $L\pi/(2\kappa)$. The integral in the denominator, however, does not admit an exact solution; an approximate analytical expression is provided in equation (23). After rearrangement, we obtain:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{2\pi \left[3(1+L) - \sqrt{(3+L)(1+3L)} \right]}{\int_{-1}^1 (1+\kappa x)^2 \sqrt{\frac{1-x^2+L^2x^2}{1-x^2}} dx} \quad (22)$$

The integral in the denominator can be evaluated using Gaussian quadrature. In particular, applying the Gauss–Chebyshev quadrature yields (Kiusalaas 2009):

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{f(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx \approx \frac{\pi}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i) \quad (23)$$

where x_i denote the quadrature nodes of integration (Kiusalaas 2009):

$$x_i = \cos \frac{(2i-1)\pi}{2n}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (24)$$

Here, n denotes the number of quadrature nodes; the accuracy of the integration improves with increasing n . Substituting equation (23) into equation (22) yields:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{2n \left[3(1+L) - \sqrt{(3+L)(1+3L)} \right]}{\sum_{i=1}^n (1+\kappa x_i)^2 \sqrt{1-x_i^2+L^2x_i^2}} \quad (25)$$

For straight circular ducts, κ and L reduce to 0 and 1, respectively; consequently, equation (25) simplifies to:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4n}{\sum_{i=1}^n 1} = \frac{4n}{n} \rightarrow \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 4 \quad (26)$$

For curved circular pipes ($L=1$), equation (25) simplifies to:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4n}{\sum_{i=1}^n (1 + \kappa x_i)^2} \rightarrow \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4n}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 + \kappa \cos \frac{(2i-1)\pi}{2n}\right)^2} \quad (27)$$

Table 1 reports the values of Bi_{Ex} for a range of nominal curvatures in elliptical ducts with different aspect ratios. As shown, Bi_{Ex} decreases with increasing curvature ratio (κ), indicating that the likelihood of dead-region formation is enhanced as κ increases.

Table 1. Bi_{Ex} for the existence of static plugs in curved elliptical ducts as a function of curvature ratio (κ) and aspect ratio (L).

Curvature Ratio (κ)	Aspect Ratio (L)						
	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.5	2	4
0.01	3.9994	3.9998	3.9998	3.9998	3.9998	3.9998	3.9993
0.1	3.9849	3.9833	3.9815	3.9801	3.9781	3.9769	3.9745
0.2	3.9414	3.9339	3.9270	3.9216	3.9140	3.9093	3.9011
0.3	3.8710	3.8543	3.8395	3.8278	3.8116	3.8016	3.7847
0.4	3.7765	3.7481	3.7233	3.7037	3.6769	3.6604	3.6329
0.5	3.6616	3.6198	3.5838	3.5556	3.5171	3.4935	3.4547
0.6	3.5304	3.4745	3.4269	3.3898	3.3396	3.3091	3.2594
0.7	3.3869	3.3172	3.2583	3.2129	3.1518	3.1149	3.0552
0.8	3.2352	3.1525	3.0833	3.0303	2.9596	2.9172	2.8492
0.9	3.0789	2.9845	2.9064	2.8470	2.7684	2.7216	2.6470

3.3. Static Plugs in Curved Rectangular Ducts

Substituting equation (10a) into equation (18) allows the analysis to be extended to curved rectangular ducts:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 16 \frac{\tilde{R}}{\tilde{d}_h} \frac{\int_{A_c} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}_c}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}_c} \rightarrow \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4(1+L)}{\kappa L} \frac{\int_{A_c} r dA_c}{\int_{\Gamma_c} r^2 d\Gamma_c} \quad (28)$$

Equation (28) can now be written as follows (only half of the cross-section is shown owing to symmetry):

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4(1+L)}{L\kappa} \frac{\int_{-1}^1 (\kappa^{-1} + x) L dx}{(\kappa^{-1} - 1)^2 L + \int_{-1}^1 (\kappa^{-1} + x)^2 dx + (\kappa^{-1} + 1)^2 L} \quad (29)$$

Thus:

$$\text{For curved rectangular ducts: } \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{12(1+L)}{3L(1+\kappa^2) + \kappa^2 + 3} \quad (30a)$$

Solutions of equation (30a) for a range of aspect ratios and curvature ratios are presented in Table 2. These data are subsequently used to examine the existence of static plugs in curved rectangular ducts. In the limiting case of curved slits, $L \rightarrow \infty$; hence, from equation (30a), we obtain:

$$\text{For curved slits: } \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \frac{4}{1+\kappa^2} \quad (30b)$$

Table 2. Bi_{Ex} for the existence of static plugs in curved rectangular ducts as a function of curvature ratio (κ) and aspect ratio (L).

Curvature Ratio (κ)	Aspect Ratio (L)								
	0.25	0.5	1	1.5	2	4	6	8	10
0.01	3.9998	3.9998	3.9997	3.9997	3.9997	3.9997	3.9996	3.9996	3.9996
0.1	3.9814	3.9779	3.9735	3.9709	3.9691	3.9656	3.9641	3.9633	3.9628
0.2	3.9267	3.9130	3.8961	3.8860	3.8793	3.8660	3.8603	3.8571	3.8551
0.3	3.8388	3.8095	3.7736	3.7523	3.7383	3.7106	3.6988	3.6923	3.6882
0.4	3.7221	3.6735	3.6145	3.5800	3.5573	3.5129	3.4942	3.4839	3.4773
0.5	3.5821	3.5122	3.4286	3.3803	3.3488	3.2877	3.2621	3.2481	3.2393
0.6	3.4247	3.3333	3.2258	3.1646	3.1250	3.0488	3.0172	3.0000	2.9891
0.7	3.2556	3.1441	3.0151	2.9426	2.8962	2.8077	2.7714	2.7516	2.7392
0.8	3.0801	2.9508	2.8037	2.7223	2.6706	2.5729	2.5332	2.5116	2.4981
0.9	2.9028	2.75860	2.5974	2.5094	2.4540	2.3502	2.3083	2.2857	2.2716

4. Static Plugs in the Critical Condition

4.1. Criterion for the Critical Condition

In this section, a general correlation for the fluidity of viscoplastic liquids in curved ducts of arbitrary cross-section is developed. The critical Bingham number is determined by optimizing the functional form of the angular momentum equation governing the flow field.

In steady, fully developed flow through curved ducts, the central moving plug undergoes rigid-body rotation (i.e., solid-like rotation arising from motion along a curved path). The velocity in this region therefore follows $\tilde{v}_\theta = \tilde{r}\tilde{\omega}$, where $\tilde{\omega}$ is a constant angular velocity. Using equation (6a), we obtain:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{r\theta} = \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{r}} - \frac{\tilde{v}_\theta}{\tilde{r}} = \tilde{\omega} - \tilde{\omega} = 0, \quad \tilde{\gamma}_{\theta z} = \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_\theta}{\partial \tilde{z}} = 0 \quad (31)$$

Note that the angular velocity is constant, and hence the angular acceleration in this region is zero. Applying an angular momentum balance to a control volume encompassing the central moving plug yields:

$$\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} \tau_0 \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma} = - \int_{\tilde{A}_p} \tilde{r} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} d\tilde{A} \quad (32)$$

where $\tilde{\Gamma}_p$ is the perimeter and \tilde{A}_p is the area of the moving plug. After simplification, equation (32) can be written as:

$$\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} \tau_0 \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma} = - \frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta} \int_{\tilde{A}_p} \tilde{R} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A} \rightarrow \frac{\tau_0}{-\frac{1}{\tilde{R}} \frac{d\tilde{p}}{d\theta}} = \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_p} \tilde{R} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}} \quad (33)$$

The flow ceases when equation (33) attains its maximum value. Equivalently, for yield-stress fluids, the critical condition is reached when the axial pressure gradient attains its minimum admissible value. Accordingly, a parameter for this critical condition can be defined as follows:

$$\tilde{K}_{Cr} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_p} \tilde{R} \tilde{r} d\tilde{A}}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} \tilde{r}^2 d\tilde{\Gamma}} \right\} \quad (34)$$

A similar formulation was previously obtained by Moyers-Gonzalez and Frigaard (2020) using an energy-based approach. In straight ducts, the radius of curvature is infinite, so there is no distinction between \tilde{R} and \tilde{r} , i.e., they are identical. In this case, equation (34) simplifies to:

$$\tilde{K}_{Cr} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{R}^2 \int_{\tilde{A}_p} d\tilde{A}}{\tilde{R}^2 \int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} d\tilde{\Gamma}} \right\} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\int_{\tilde{A}_p} d\tilde{A}}{\int_{\tilde{\Gamma}_p} d\tilde{\Gamma}} \right\} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\text{mes}(\tilde{A}_p)}{\text{mes}(\tilde{\Gamma}_p)} \right\} \quad (35)$$

The above equation is consistent with the formulation previously presented by Mosolov and Miasnikov (1967) for the fluidity condition of viscoplastic liquids in straight ducts.

4.2. Topology of Static Plugs

The stopping condition of the flow is given by equation (34). At this stage, the topology of the plug region is not known, i.e., the shape of the dead region remains undetermined; we therefore represent it by a function $y(x)$ to be determined. Accordingly, equation (34) can be written as:

$$\tilde{K}_{Cr} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{R} \int (\tilde{R} + \tilde{x}) \tilde{y} d\tilde{x}}{\int (\tilde{R} + \tilde{x})^2 \sqrt{1 + \tilde{y}'^2} d\tilde{x}} \right\} \rightarrow K_{Cr} = \frac{\tilde{K}_{Cr}}{\tilde{a}} = \text{Sup} \left\{ \frac{\int (1 + \kappa x) y dx}{\int (1 + \kappa x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} dx} \right\} \quad (36)$$

Equation (36) defines a nonlinear fractional programming problem. Various approaches may be employed to solve such problems, including change-of-variable techniques, direct methods, parametric methods, and monotonic projective algorithms. In the present study, the parametric method is adopted. Accordingly, an equivalent nonlinear problem to equation (36) is solved, given by (Stancu-Minasian 1997):

$$Q(\lambda) : \max \hat{f}(x) - \lambda \hat{g}(x), \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R} \quad (37a)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f} &= \int F dx, & F &= (1 + \kappa x)y \\ \hat{g} &= \int G dx, & G &= (1 + \kappa x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} \end{aligned} \quad (37b)$$

Here, a hybrid functional, H , is introduced to solve equation (37):

$$H = F - \lambda G \rightarrow H = (1 + \kappa x)y - \lambda (1 + \kappa x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} \quad (38)$$

where λ is an unknown constant (Lagrange multiplier). The Euler–Lagrange equation corresponding to the optimization of equation (38) is given by:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial y} - \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial y'} \right) = 0 \quad (39)$$

Substituting H from equation (38) into equation (39) yields:

$$-\lambda \frac{d}{dx} \left((1 + \kappa x)^2 \frac{y'}{\sqrt{1 + y'^2}} \right) = (1 + \kappa x) \quad (40)$$

Integrating both sides of equation (40) gives:

$$-\lambda (1 + \kappa x)^2 \frac{y'}{\sqrt{1 + y'^2}} = \frac{\kappa}{2} x^2 + x + c_1 \quad (41)$$

The functions y' and y in equation (41) can now be determined as:

$$y' = \pm \frac{\frac{\kappa}{2} x^2 + x + c_1}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 (1 + \kappa x)^4 - \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} x^2 + x + c_1 \right)^2}} \xrightarrow{\text{Integration}} y = \pm [f(x) - f(x_0)] - c_2 \quad (42)$$

Since the explicit expression of $f(x)$ in Eq. (42) is quite lengthy, it is presented in Appendix A. Alternatively, the integral in Eq. (42) can be evaluated numerically using straightforward methods

such as the trapezoidal or Simpson's rule. For this purpose, it is convenient to retain the term $f(x_0)$, where x_0 denotes the starting point of the numerical integration. With this formulation, the quantity $f(x) - f(x_0) = \int_{x_0}^x y'(s) ds$ is computed, ensuring that its value is zero at $x = x_0$. This initialization simplifies the numerical procedure and enhances computational stability. Finally, the unknown parameters in Eq. (42) are determined by maximizing Eq. (34) while satisfying the appropriate boundary conditions corresponding to the geometry of the cross-section and the curvature ratio.

In the limiting case of straight ducts $\kappa = 0$, Eq. (42) can be written as:

$$y = \pm \int \frac{x+c_1}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 - (x+c_1)^2}} dx = \pm \sqrt{\lambda^2 - (x+c_1)^2} - c_2 \rightarrow (x+c_1)^2 + (y+c_2)^2 = \lambda^2 \quad (43)$$

Obviously, Eq. (43) represents a circular arc. Accordingly, the shape of the static plug (dead region) in straight-duct flow reduces to a circular arc, consistent with the classical results of Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966).

In the presence of curvature, the axial pressure gradient becomes spatially nonuniform, varying radially. This variation directly influences the shape of the static plugs (dead regions). Since the pressure decreases along the curvature, dead regions are more likely to develop near the duct's outer wall.

As shown by Eq. (A3), the governing equation for the plug topology becomes significantly more complex in curved geometries compared with straight channels. The resulting solution indicates that the shape of the dead region can be interpreted as a non-trivial combination of elliptic functions.

4.3. A variational criterion for optimal plug configurations in curved ducts

The variational formulation developed in the previous section provides a natural framework for characterizing the structure of unyielded regions in curved ducts. In particular, the critical condition corresponds to the maximization of a weighted functional that balances the driving moment induced by the pressure gradient with the resisting moment due to the yield stress along

the boundary of the plug region. This formulation allows the problem to be interpreted as a weighted optimization problem over all admissible subsets of the cross-section. In contrast to the classical Cheeger problem for straight ducts, curvature introduces radial weighting into both the area and boundary contributions, fundamentally altering the geometry of the optimal set. An important question arising from this formulation is whether the optimal set coincides with the entire cross-section or corresponds to a proper subset bounded by a free boundary. This distinction determines whether a separated static plug forms within the cross-section or whether the unyielded region occupies the entire domain.

This variational structure naturally suggests the introduction of weighted geometric measures on admissible subsets of the cross-section. Let Ω be a bounded convex cross-section of a curved duct, and let $D \subseteq \Omega$ be an admissible subset. Define the weighted area and perimeter by

$$A_\kappa(D) = \int_D (1 + \kappa x) dA \quad (44)$$

$$P_\kappa(D) = \int_{\partial D} (1 + \kappa x)^2 d\Gamma \quad (45)$$

which represent, respectively, the driving and resisting contributions appearing in the variational formulation. The associated ratio

$$M_\kappa(D) = \frac{P_\kappa(D)}{A_\kappa(D)} \quad (46)$$

defines a weighted Cheeger-type ratio, and we denote

$$h_\kappa(\Omega) = \inf_{D \subset \Omega} M_\kappa(D) \quad (47)$$

Theorem (Weighted Cheeger-type criterion for plug formation in curved ducts)

if

$$M_\kappa(\Omega) = h_\kappa(\Omega) \quad (48)$$

then

$$\Omega_c^\kappa = \Omega \quad (49)$$

and no separated static plug with an internal free boundary can occur. Conversely, a separated plug can occur only if there exists a proper subset $D \subsetneq \Omega$ such that

$$M_\kappa(D) \leq M_\kappa(\Omega) \quad (50)$$

with strict inequality if Ω is not itself a minimizer.

Proof.

From the variational formulation of §4 (Eq. (36)), the critical configuration maximizes

$$K_\kappa(D) = \frac{A_\kappa(D)}{P_\kappa(D)} \quad (51)$$

This is equivalent to minimizing $M_\kappa(D)$, and therefore the variational problem reduces to the definition of the weighted Cheeger constant $h_\kappa(\Omega)$ given in (47).

Assume that

$$M_\kappa(\Omega) = h_\kappa(\Omega) \quad (52)$$

Then Ω minimizes the functional. Hence, no proper subset $D \subset \Omega$ can yield a smaller value of M_κ , and the maximizer of K_κ is attained at $D = \Omega$. It follows that

$$\Omega_c^\kappa = \Omega \quad (53)$$

and therefore no separated plug can form. Conversely, suppose that a separated plug exists. Then its domain corresponds to a proper subset $D \subset \Omega$ achieving the variational optimum, i.e.

$$M_\kappa(D) = h_\kappa(\Omega) \quad (54)$$

which immediately yields

$$M_\kappa(D) \leq M_\kappa(\Omega) \quad (55)$$

with strict inequality if Ω is not itself optimal.

To determine the geometry of the free boundary, let the interface be described by $y = y(x)$. Using the dimensionless formulation consistent with (42), the functional becomes

$$K_\kappa[y] = \frac{\int (1 + \kappa x) y dx}{\int (1 + \kappa x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} dx} \quad (56)$$

Introducing a Lagrange multiplier λ , define

$$H = (1 + \kappa x) y - \lambda (1 + \kappa x)^2 \sqrt{1 + y'^2} \quad (57)$$

The Euler–Lagrange equation yields

$$\lambda \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{(1 + \kappa x)^2 y'}{\sqrt{1 + y'^2}} \right) = -(1 + \kappa x) \quad (58)$$

Using the standard curvature definition,

$$\chi_f = \frac{y''}{(1 + y'^2)^{3/2}} \quad (59)$$

and differentiating the free-boundary equation associated with Eq. (42), one obtains

$$\chi_f = -\frac{1}{\lambda(1 + \kappa x)} - \frac{2\kappa}{1 + \kappa x} \frac{y'}{\sqrt{1 + y'^2}} \quad (60)$$

Thus, the free-boundary curvature is not constant when $\kappa \neq 0$, in contrast with the classical Cheeger problem.

Finally, in the limit $\kappa \rightarrow 0$,

$$M_\kappa(D) \rightarrow \frac{P(D)}{A(D)} \quad (61)$$

which recovers the classical Cheeger problem.

Curvature Compatibility Criterion

Let $D^* \subseteq \Omega$ denote the optimal stagnant region associated with the minimization of the weighted functional M_κ . Here, $P_\kappa(\cdot)$ and $A_\kappa(\cdot)$ denote the weighted perimeter and area introduced previously, κ is the curvature parameter, and (x, y) are the local Cartesian coordinates in the cross-section. The boundary is parameterized by arc-length s , and χ denotes curvature.

As established above, the boundary of the optimal set must satisfy the Euler–Lagrange condition, which prescribes the curvature of the free boundary $\chi_f(s)$ as a function of the local geometry and κ . In general, this curvature varies spatially.

In the special case where the entire cross-section is optimal, i.e.

$$D^* = \Omega \tag{62}$$

no internal free boundary exists. Therefore, the domain boundary $\partial\Omega$ must satisfy the same optimality condition. Denoting its curvature by $\chi_{\partial\Omega}(s)$, this leads to the compatibility requirement

$$\chi_{\partial\Omega}(s) = \chi_f(s), \quad s \in \partial\Omega \tag{63}$$

Substituting $D^* = \Omega$ into the Euler–Lagrange curvature expression yields a geometric condition along the boundary involving the ratio $P_\kappa(\Omega)/A_\kappa(\Omega)$, the parameter κ , and the local slope $y'(s)$.

To assess whether this condition is satisfied, we introduce the residual function:

$$\mathcal{R}(s) = \chi_{\partial\Omega}(s) + \frac{1}{1 + \kappa x(s)} \frac{P_\kappa(\Omega)}{A_\kappa(\Omega)} + \frac{2\kappa}{1 + \kappa x(s)} \frac{y'(s)}{\sqrt{1 + y'(s)^2}} \tag{64}$$

The condition for the absence of a separated static plug is then

$$\mathcal{R}(s) = 0 \quad \text{for all } s \in \partial\Omega \tag{65}$$

If, on the other hand,

$$\exists s \in \partial\Omega \quad \text{such that} \quad \mathcal{R}(s) \neq 0 \tag{66}$$

then the boundary fails to satisfy the optimality condition, and the optimal set must be a proper subset of the domain:

$$D^* \subsetneq \Omega \quad (67)$$

indicating the formation of a separated static plug.

This criterion provides a local geometric interpretation of the global variational problem: the existence of a separated static plug is determined by the compatibility between the intrinsic curvature of the domain boundary and the curvature prescribed by the Euler–Lagrange condition.

The curvature compatibility condition derived above can be related to the classical Cheeger formulation in the limit of vanishing curvature parameter. Indeed, as $\kappa \rightarrow 0$, the weighting becomes uniform and the Euler–Lagrange curvature reduces to a constant:

$$\chi_f(s) \rightarrow -\frac{P(\Omega)}{A(\Omega)} \quad \text{as } \kappa \rightarrow 0 \quad (68)$$

Accordingly, the compatibility condition

$$\chi_{\partial\Omega}(s) = -\frac{P(\Omega)}{A(\Omega)} \quad (69)$$

Since the right-hand side is constant, this condition can only be satisfied if the domain boundary is compatible with a constant-curvature free boundary. In this limit, the problem reduces to the classical Cheeger formulation, where optimality is expressed through the inequality:

$$\bar{\chi}_{\partial\Omega} A(\Omega) \leq P(\Omega) \quad (70)$$

where $\bar{\chi}_{\partial\Omega}$ denotes the maximum boundary curvature. Therefore, in the limit $\kappa \rightarrow 0$, the curvature compatibility criterion reduces to the classical Cheeger formulation, consistent with Theorem 2 of Georgiou and Huilgol (2023). This highlights that the present formulation constitutes a curvature-weighted generalization of the classical Cheeger problem, with the latter recovered as the limiting case of straight ducts.

5. Critical condition for common cross-sectional shapes

5.1. Curved elliptical ducts

General criteria for flow cessation and the topology of dead regions are given by Eqs. (34) and (42). A schematic illustration of these regions is shown in Figure 2. The constraints required to determine the unknown parameters for the outer dead region are outlined below. For clarity, the subscript o is used to denote the constants associated with the outer region (i.e., c_1 , c_2 and λ).

The equation describing the wall shape in elliptical ducts is as follows:

$$y = L\sqrt{1-x^2} \quad (71)$$

The derivatives of the wall profile and the interface of the outer dead region at their intersection point ($x = x_0$) can be obtained from Eqs. (42) and (71):

$$\text{For the wall:} \quad y'|_{x=x_0} = -\alpha_o \quad \rightarrow \quad \alpha_o = \frac{Lx_0}{\sqrt{1-x_0^2}} \quad (72a)$$

$$\text{For the interface of the outer dead region:} \quad y'|_{x=x_0} = \frac{-(\beta_o + c_{1,o})}{\sqrt{\lambda_o^2 \Upsilon_o^4 - (\beta_o + c_{1,o})^2}} \quad \& \quad \begin{cases} \beta_o = \kappa x_0^2 / 2 + x_0 \\ \Upsilon_o = 1 + \kappa x_0 \end{cases} \quad (72b)$$

Since the dead region forms continuously from the wall, the derivatives of the interface of the dead region and the wall must be equal at the intersection point ($x = x_0$).

$$\frac{\beta_o + c_{1,o}}{\sqrt{\lambda_o^2 \Upsilon_o^4 - (\beta_o + c_{1,o})^2}} = \alpha_o \quad \rightarrow \quad \beta_o + c_{1,o} = \frac{\alpha_o \lambda_o \Upsilon_o^2}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_o^2}} \quad (73)$$

At the intersection between the dead region and the symmetry plane, the following condition holds:

$$\text{At } x = x_1: \quad \frac{dy}{dx} \rightarrow \infty \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{dx}{dy} = 0 \quad (74)$$

It follows from Eqs. (42) and (74) that:

$$\lambda_o^2 \Upsilon_1^4 - (\beta_1 + c_{1,o})^2 = 0 \rightarrow \lambda_o = \frac{\beta_1 + c_{1,o}}{\Upsilon_1^2} \quad \& \quad \begin{cases} \beta_1 = \kappa x_1^2 / 2 + x_1 \\ \Upsilon_1 = 1 + \kappa x_1 \end{cases} \quad (75)$$

Using Eqs. (73) and (75), the constant c_1 can be expressed as follows:

$$c_{1,o} = \frac{\alpha_o \beta_1 (\Upsilon_0 / \Upsilon_1)^2 - \beta_0 \sqrt{1 + \alpha_o^2}}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_o^2} - \alpha_o (\Upsilon_0 / \Upsilon_1)^2} \quad (76)$$

Based on the coordinates of points A and B in Figure 2, the following relations are obtained:

$$\text{At } x = x_0: y = L\sqrt{1 - x_0^2} \rightarrow c_{2,o} = -L\sqrt{1 - x_0^2} \quad (77)$$

$$\text{At } x = x_1: y = 0 \rightarrow f(x_1) - f(x_0) + c_{2,o} = 0 \quad (78)$$

Here, there are five unknowns, $c_{1,o}$, $c_{2,o}$, x_0 , x_1 and λ_o , but only four boundary conditions are available (Eqs. (75) – (78)). If x_0 is specified, the remaining unknowns can be determined sequentially. First, $c_{2,o}$ is obtained from Eq. (77). The expressions for λ_o and $c_{1,o}$ from Eqs. (75) and (76) are then substituted into Eq. (78), which is solved using a root-finding procedure (here, the Newton–Raphson method) to determine x_1 . The term $f(x_1) - f(x_0)$ appearing in Eq. (78), can be evaluated from Eq. (42) in the interval of $[x_0, x_1]$ using standard numerical or analytical integration. Finally, $c_{1,o}$ and λ_o are computed from Eqs. (76) and (77). Accordingly, the shape of the dead region is fully determined once x_0 is specified.

The same procedure applies to the inner dead region. The corresponding set of equations is given by:

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\beta_3 + c_{1,i}}{\Upsilon_3^2} \quad (79a)$$

$$c_{1,i} = \frac{-\left(\alpha_i \beta_3 (\Upsilon_2 / \Upsilon_3)^2 + \beta_2 \sqrt{1 + \alpha_i^2}\right)}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_i^2} + \alpha_i (\Upsilon_2 / \Upsilon_3)^2} \quad (79b)$$

$$c_{2,i} = -L\sqrt{1-x_i^2} \quad (79c)$$

$$f(x_3) - f(x_2) + c_{2,i} = 0 \quad (79d)$$

where $\beta_j = \kappa x_j^2 / 2 + x_j$ and $\gamma_j = 1 + \kappa x_j$ for $j = 2, 3$, and α_i is defined as:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{Lx_2}{\sqrt{1-x_2^2}} \quad (80)$$

Fig. 2. The schematic shape of static plugs of curved elliptical ducts for $L < 1$.

In a manner analogous to the outer dead region, the constants $c_{1,i}$, $c_{2,i}$, x_3 and λ_i can be determined from Eqs. (79a) – (79d) once x_2 is specified. Accordingly, the unknowns of the problem reduce to

x_0 and x_2 , which represent the initial points of the outer and inner dead-region profiles, respectively. These quantities are obtained by maximizing the functional defined in Eq. (34).

The optimization is performed using a simulated annealing algorithm, which is well-suited to unconstrained problems. The search is restricted to physically admissible bound for x_0 and x_2 , $[-1,1]$ which are readily determined from the geometry of the cross-section.

The shape of the dead region is strongly dependent on the aspect ratio L . In straight elliptical ducts, the minimum wall shear stress occurs at the extremities of the major axis; therefore, dead regions may develop at these locations when the yield stress exceeds the local shear stress. In curved elliptical ducts with $L < 1$, the distribution of dead regions is further influenced by curvature. As the curvature ratio increases, the outer dead region expands, whereas the inner one shrinks. The corresponding critical Bingham number is evaluated from $\text{Bi}_{Cr} = 16\tilde{K}_{Cr} / \tilde{d}_h$.

To assess the accuracy of the proposed formulation, the theoretical predictions are compared with three-dimensional numerical simulations performed using COMSOL Multiphysics. The simulations are conducted for creeping flow of a Bingham fluid in a 270° curved duct. The governing equations are those given in Eqs. (2) and (3); however, for numerical implementation, the Bingham constitutive equation is regularized using the Papanastasiou model. A sufficiently large value of the regularization parameter m is employed to ensure a close approximation to the ideal Bingham limit.

A systematic grid refinement study is first performed to verify the spatial convergence of the numerical solution. Grid independence is established by comparing solutions obtained on progressively refined meshes. In addition, sensitivity tests with respect to the regularization parameter m confirm that the results are insensitive to further increases in m , indicating that the predicted flow field and plug topology are not affected by the numerical regularization.

The inlet and outlet pressures are prescribed such that the flow remains close to the critical condition. Owing to the creeping-flow regime, the flow develops rapidly along the duct; nevertheless, the velocity field is evaluated at $\theta = 135^\circ$, which is sufficiently far from the inlet and lies well within the fully developed region. Figure 3 compares the predicted shapes of the static plug regions in curved circular and elliptical ducts, obtained from the optimization of Eq.

(34) in conjunction with Eq. (42), with the corresponding three-dimensional numerical results. Since numerical simulations at the exact critical condition are not feasible, the computations are performed in its vicinity, which results in slightly smaller plug regions compared to the theoretical predictions. Nevertheless, the agreement between the predicted and computed plug shapes is very good. The results also indicate that the growth of the static plug accelerates rapidly as the flow approaches the critical condition; this behaviour is not specific to curved ducts and is also observed in other configurations, such as straight channels.

Figure 3. Static plug shapes in curved circular and elliptical ducts: predictions from maximization of Eq. (34) using Eq. (42) (left) and CFD simulations (right).

Figure 4 shows the distribution and symmetry-plane profiles of the dimensionless axial velocity v_θ for two representative cases close to flow cessation. The imposed Bingham numbers are not taken exactly at the critical values, since numerical simulations become increasingly difficult as the limiting state is approached; however, the velocity magnitudes remain very small, of order 10^{-4} for $L=1, \kappa = 0.65$ and 10^{-5} for $L=2, \kappa = 0.4$, indicating that both computations lie in the near-critical regime. For these geometries, the corresponding critical Bingham numbers are $Bi_{Cr} \approx 3.33$ for $L=1, \kappa = 0.65$ and $Bi_{Cr} \approx 3.66$ for $L=2, \kappa = 0.4$, so that the imposed values are slightly below Bi_{Cr} , and the flow remains weakly mobile while being close to complete arrest. In the central part of the cross-section, v_θ varies approximately linearly with the radial coordinate, which is characteristic of rigid-body rotation and consistent with the assumption $v_\theta = r\omega$ used in the critical-state formulation, indicating that this region corresponds to a moving unyielded plug. In contrast, a rapid decay of v_θ is observed near the outer wall, where the velocity approaches zero, forming a near-zero-velocity region that coincides with the static plug predicted in Fig. 3; this indicates that flow arrest first develops along the outer wall due to curvature-induced stress redistribution. The influence of geometry is also evident from the comparison between the two cases: for $L = 1$, the stagnant region remains confined to a relatively narrow layer near the outer wall, whereas for $L = 2$, the velocity field extends along the major axis and the near-zero-velocity region becomes more pronounced, indicating a state closer to complete flow arrest. The velocity field in Fig. 4 is therefore consistent with the predicted plug topology (Fig. 3), with flow arrest developing near the outer wall as the critical condition is approached.

The shapes of the dead regions in curved elliptical ducts for different curvature ratios at $L = 0.2$ are shown in Fig. 5. For small curvature ratios, dead regions may form on both the inner and outer sides of the duct. As the curvature ratio κ increases, the outer dead region expands, while the inner dead region progressively shrinks. Eventually, the inner dead region vanishes at $\kappa = 0.8$. This behavior reflects the redistribution of the axial pressure gradient across the cross-section, with a decrease near the outer wall and an increase near the inner wall as curvature increases.

$L = 1, \kappa = 0.65, \text{Re}_B = 0.01 \text{ \& } \text{Bi} = 3.2$

$L = 2, \kappa = 0.4, \text{Re}_B = 0.01 \text{ \& } \text{Bi} = 3.6$

Fig. 4. Distribution (left column) and symmetry-plane profiles (right column) of the dimensionless axial velocity v_θ in curved ducts for two cases close to the critical condition.

The corresponding critical Bingham numbers, Bi_{Cr} , for viscoplastic flow in curved elliptical ducts are reported in Table 3. According to Lemma 3.1, static plugs are guaranteed to exist when $Bi_{Ex} < Bi_{Cr}$. The shaded entries in Table 3 indicate cases satisfying this condition. For small curvature ratios and aspect ratios, this inequality is not satisfied, and no dead regions are formed, consistent with the absence of shaded entries in those cases.

The same framework can be applied to curved circular ducts by setting $L = 1$. In this case, the inner dead region does not form, and static plugs develop only near the outer wall once the curvature ratio exceeds a threshold value. The corresponding shapes are shown in Fig. 6. Similar to straight pipes, no static plug is observed for $\kappa \lesssim 0.38$. At larger curvature ratios, a small dead region first appears near the outer wall and then grows with increasing κ , eventually occupying a significant portion of the cross-section.

As discussed earlier, the topology of the static plug depends on the aspect ratio. The schematic configurations for $L > 1$ are shown in Fig. 7. For small curvature ratios, two separate dead regions form near the upper and lower walls, each tangent to both the inner and outer boundaries (see Fig. 7a). Owing to symmetry, it is sufficient to determine one of these regions. In this case, the constants appearing in the interface description of the dead region are given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{\beta_0 - \beta_1}{\frac{\alpha_0 \Upsilon_0^2}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_0^2}} - \frac{\alpha_1 \Upsilon_1^2}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_1^2}}} \quad (81a)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{\alpha_0 \lambda \Upsilon_0^2}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha_0^2}} - \beta_0 \quad (81b)$$

$$c_2 = -L \sqrt{1 - x_0^2} \quad (81c)$$

$$f(x_1) - f(x_0) = L \left(\sqrt{1 - x_1^2} - \sqrt{1 - x_0^2} \right) \quad (81d)$$

Similar to the previous cases, the constants c_1 , c_2 , x_1 , and λ are determined from Eqns. (81a)–(81d) once the value of x_0 is specified. The problem, therefore, reduces to determining x_0 , which is obtained by maximizing the functional defined in equation (34). For sufficiently large curvature ratios κ , the two dead regions located at the upper and lower parts of the cross-section can merge to form a single connected region (see Fig. 7b). The corresponding shapes of the dead regions for curved elliptical ducts with $L = 5$ are shown in Fig. 8. For small κ , the dead regions appear as two distinct plugs adjacent to the upper and lower walls. As κ increases, these regions extend towards

the outer wall, reflecting the redistribution of the axial pressure gradient across the section. At $\kappa = 0.8$, the two regions coalesce, forming a single continuous dead region.

As shown in Fig. 6, for sufficiently small values of κ in the curved circular pipes, no static plug forms at the wall. This behavior depends not only on the duct's curvature ratio but also on its cross-sectional topology. Using the curvature-compatibility framework developed in §4.3, the onset of wall-attached static plugs can be examined. In particular, this framework enables the determination of the bounds of the no-static-plug regime in terms of curvature and aspect ratio for curved elliptical ducts, based on the analysis presented in §4.3 (see Eqs. (64) and (65)), which are given as follows:

We consider the domain Ω , defined previously in (71) for an elliptical cross-section, and parameterize its boundary as

$$x = \cos t, \quad y = L \sin t, \quad 0 \leq t \leq \pi \quad (82)$$

The boundary curvature follows from the standard parametric expression. With the sign convention adopted in (63), one obtains

$$\chi_{\partial\Omega}(t) = -\frac{L}{\left(\sin^2 t + L^2 \cos^2 t\right)^{3/2}} \quad (83)$$

and the geometric term entering the Euler–Lagrange relation is

$$\frac{y'}{\sqrt{1+y'^2}} = -\frac{L \cos t}{\sqrt{\sin^2 t + L^2 \cos^2 t}} \quad (84)$$

For the full cross-section, the weighted perimeter-to-area ratio is

$$Q_L(\kappa) = \frac{1}{\pi L} \int_0^{2\pi} (1 + \kappa \cos \phi)^2 \sqrt{\sin^2 \phi + L^2 \cos^2 \phi} d\phi \quad (85)$$

Owing to symmetry, the term linear in κ vanishes, so that $Q_L(\kappa)$ is an even function of κ . Substituting (82), (84), and (85) into the curvature relation (64), and evaluating the condition at a boundary point corresponding to plug onset, gives

$$Q_L(\kappa) = \frac{L(1 + \kappa \cos t)}{(\sin^2 t + L^2 \cos^2 t)^{3/2}} + \frac{2\kappa L \cos t}{\sqrt{\sin^2 t + L^2 \cos^2 t}} \quad (86)$$

A curvature-compatible onset point exists if there is at least one $t \in [0, \pi]$ satisfying (86). The onset of a separated static plug is therefore characterized by the existence of such a boundary point. Accordingly, the critical curvature ratio is defined as

$$\kappa_c(L) = \inf \{ \kappa \in [0, 1) : \exists t \in [0, \pi] \text{ such that } Q_L(\kappa) = F_L(t, \kappa) \} \quad (87)$$

where the right-hand side of (86) defines $F_L(t, \kappa)$. Equivalently,

$$Q_L(\kappa_c) = \max_{0 \leq t \leq \pi} F_L(t, \kappa_c) \quad (88)$$

with κ_c denoting the smallest value of κ for which a curvature-compatible boundary point appears. The details of the solution of (88), based on (85) and (86), are provided in Appendix B. In the following, the results of this analysis for selected limiting cases are presented:

- **Curved circular pipes**

For the circular limit $L = 1$, Eq. (85) gives

$$Q_1(\kappa) = 2 + \kappa^2 \quad (89)$$

Moreover, from the definition of F_L , one obtains (substituting $L=1$ into Eq. (86)):

$$F_1(t, \kappa) = 1 + 3\kappa \cos t \quad (90)$$

Since the maximum occurs at $t = 0$, the onset condition $Q_L(\kappa_c) = \max F_L(t, \kappa_c)$ gives

$$2 + \kappa_c^2 = 1 + 3\kappa_c \quad (91)$$

Therefore,

$$\kappa_c(1) = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2} \approx 0.382 \quad (92)$$

This recovers the curved circular-pipe result obtained from the curvature-compatibility criterion. Therefore, no static plug forms in curved circular pipes for $\kappa < 0.382$. This provides a local geometric criterion for the onset of wall-attached static plugs and, in particular, identifies the boundary of the no-static-plug regime. Biomedically, this condition ($\kappa < 0.382$) provides a design rule for vascular grafts and sclerotherapy channels to avoid static plug formation and its associated risks (thrombosis or ineffective foam displacement)

- **Straight elliptical ducts**

The present formulation can also be used to identify the aspect ratio for which no static plug exists in straight elliptical ducts. In the straight-duct limit ($\kappa = 0$), from (B1) and (B4a) we obtain:

$$Q_L = \frac{4}{\pi L} E(1 - L^2) \quad (93)$$

where $E(k)$ denotes the complete elliptic integral function of the second kind (see Eq. (B4b) in Appendix B). In the straight-duct limit ($\kappa = 0$), (B7a) reduces to:

$$\max F_L = \frac{1}{L^2} \quad (94)$$

Substituting (93) and (94) into (88) yields

$$\frac{4}{\pi L} E(1 - L^2) = \frac{1}{L^2} \rightarrow \frac{4L}{\pi} E(\sqrt{1 - L^2}) = 1 \quad (95)$$

which determines the critical aspect ratio L_c . Solving Eq. (95) gives

$$L_c \approx 0.61, \quad \frac{1}{L_c} \approx 1.63 \quad (96)$$

This limiting result recovers the classical Cheeger-type condition for straight elliptical ducts and agrees with Georgiou and Huilgol (2023), providing a consistency check for the present curvature-based formulation.

Figure 9 summarises the topology of the dead regions at the critical condition over a range of aspect ratios L and curvature ratios κ . Region (I) corresponds to configurations for which no appreciable static plug is present; in this regime, the critical Bingham number coincides with Bi_{EX} (to four decimal places). For these cases, any unyielded region remains negligible and does not affect the overall flow structure. Here, the boundary of the no-static-plug regime (the red curve around Region (I) in Fig. 9) is determined from the solution of the algebraic equations (B8a)–(B8b). In particular, for a given aspect ratio L , the critical curvature ratio κ_c is obtained by solving these equations and selecting the smallest admissible root. This procedure defines the locus separating configurations with no wall-attached static plug from those in which a plug first appears. Notably, this prediction is consistent with the plug shapes obtained independently from the direct solution of (34) and (42) using a simulated annealing optimization procedure.

As shown in Fig. 9, at sufficiently large curvature ratios, a static plug forms near the outer wall for all values of L (Region (II)), indicating that curvature is the dominant mechanism driving flow arrest. In contrast, Regions (III) and (IV) correspond to configurations with two separated plugs located near the extremities of the major axis. The transition between these regimes for $\kappa = 0$, is governed by the critical aspect ratios identified from the straight-duct limit, namely $L_c \approx 0.61$ and its reciprocal $1/L_c \approx 1.63$ (refer to Eq. (96)).

For $L > 1.63$ (Region (III)) and small κ , the two plugs are symmetric and of equal size. As κ increases, they progressively approach each other and eventually merge, leading to a transition towards the single outer-wall plug observed in Region (II). For $L < 0.61$ (Region (IV)), the two plugs become asymmetric, with the outer plug larger than the inner one due to the curvature-induced bias. With increasing κ , the inner plug is progressively suppressed and may ultimately vanish, leaving a dominant outer dead region consistent with Region (II).

Figure 5. Variation of static plug shapes in curved elliptical ducts at $L = 0.2$ with curvature ratio (κ).

Figure 6. Variation of static plug shapes in curved circular pipes with curvature ratio (κ).

Figure 7. Schematic of static plug topology in curved elliptical ducts for $L > 1$: (a) separated outer plugs; (b) merged outer plugs.

Figure 8. Variation of static plug shapes in curved elliptical ducts at $L = 5$ with curvature ratio (κ).

Table 3. Bi_{Cr} for viscoplastic flow in curved elliptical ducts as a function of curvature ratio (κ) and aspect ratio (L).

Curvature Ratio (κ)	Aspect Ratio (L)						
	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.5	2	4
0.01	4.0937	4.0014	3.9998	3.9998	3.9998	4.0013	4.0934
0.1	4.0971	3.9887	3.9815	3.9801	3.9781	3.9786	4.0679
0.2	4.1091	3.9535	3.9270	3.9216	3.9140	3.9111	3.9923
0.3	4.1326	3.9044	3.8417	3.8278	3.8116	3.8036	3.8725
0.4	4.1739	3.8518	3.7375	3.7037	3.6769	3.6628	3.7163
0.5	4.2421	3.8067	3.6293	3.5593	3.5171	3.4966	3.5332
0.6	4.3521	3.7811	3.5322	3.4161	3.3396	3.3132	3.3326
0.7	4.5310	3.7907	3.4610	3.2947	3.1583	3.1207	3.1231
0.8	4.8390	3.8649	3.4374	3.2162	3.0162	2.9416	2.9089
0.9	5.4644	4.0894	3.5175	3.2232	2.9471	2.8305	2.7219

White and gray cells denote the absence and presence of static plugs, respectively.

Figure 9. Regime map of static plug topology in curved elliptical ducts at the critical condition in the (κ, L) plane. Different regions correspond to distinct plug topologies.

5.2. Curved Rectangular Ducts

Schematic shapes of the static plug in curved rectangular ducts are shown in Figure 10. At small curvature ratios, plugs may form near the corners (see figure 10a). This behavior is similar to that in straight ducts, except that the outer plugs may be larger than the inner ones. As shown, the slopes of these curves are zero at x_0 and x_1 , and become infinite at $x = \pm 1$; thus, the unknown constants of the outer plug region located above the x -axis can be determined as follows:

$$\lambda_o = \frac{\frac{\kappa}{2}(1-x_0^2) + (1-x_0)}{(1+\kappa)^2} \quad (97a)$$

$$c_{1,o} = -\frac{\kappa}{2}x_0^2 - x_0 \quad (97b)$$

$$c_{2,o} = -L \quad (97c)$$

Similarly, the unknown constants associated with the inner static plug above the x -axis are obtained as:

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\frac{\kappa}{2}(1-x_2^2) - (1+x_2)}{(1-\kappa)^2} \quad (98a)$$

$$c_{1,i} = -\frac{\kappa}{2}x_2^2 - x_2 \quad (98b)$$

$$c_{2,i} = -L \quad (98c)$$

Increasing the curvature ratio increases the size of the outer plugs. At sufficiently large curvature ratios, these plugs may merge to form a continuous outer region (see Figure 10b). To determine the threshold for this transition, we begin with the solution corresponding to separated plugs (as in Figure 10a) and increase the curvature ratio up to the value at which

$$y_o(1) = f_o(1) - c_{2,o} = 0$$

At this point, the outer plugs meet at $x = 1$ and merge for larger curvature ratios. For these cases, the point at which the slope becomes infinite shifts from $x = \pm 1$ to $x = x_1$. The unknown constants for the outer plug region can then be determined as follows:

$$\lambda_o = \frac{\frac{\kappa}{2}(x_1^2 - x_0^2) + (x_1 - x_0)}{(1+\kappa x_1)^2} \quad (99a)$$

$$c_{1,o} = -\frac{\kappa}{2} x_0^2 - x_0 \quad (99b)$$

$$c_{2,o} = -L \quad (99c)$$

$$f_o(x_1) - f_o(x_0) = -L \quad (99d)$$

If the value of x_0 is known, the remaining constants (i.e. x_1 , λ_o and $c_{1,o}$) can be determined from (99a–d). As in the case of elliptical ducts, a root-finding procedure is required to solve (99d) and determine x_1 . The unknown parameters of the problem, namely x_0 and x_2 , for both configurations shown in Figures 10(a) and 10 (b), are obtained by maximizing the functional defined in (34).

Figure 10. Schematic of static plug configurations in curved rectangular ducts, showing (a) separated outer plugs and (b) merged outer plugs.

The present results are validated against the classical solution of Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966) for viscoplastic flow in straight rectangular ducts. This comparison is carried out by considering the limiting case of an infinitesimal curvature ratio in the present formulation, whereby the curved-

duct geometry reduces to the straight-duct configuration. Table 4 summarizes the corresponding critical Bingham numbers over a wide range of aspect ratios. As shown, the predictions of the present study are in excellent agreement with those reported by Mosolov & Miasnikov (1966), with only negligible differences attributable to numerical precision. This close agreement confirms the correctness of the present formulation and its consistency with established results in the limiting case of straight ducts.

Table 4. Critical Bingham number for viscoplastic flow in straight rectangular ducts.

Aspect Ratio (L)	1	2	4	8	12	20	100
Mosolov and Miasnikov (1966)	4.2413	4.2114	4.1477	4.0886	4.0629	4.0397	4.0085
Present study	4.2412	4.2113	4.1477	4.0886	4.0629	4.0397	4.0085

As a second test case, the present results are compared with those reported by Roberts & Cox (2020). They derived an analytical solution for the critical condition of viscoplastic flow in curved slits (parallel curved plates). The corresponding critical Bingham number reported by Roberts & Cox (2020) is given by:

$$\text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}} = 4 \left[1 - \frac{k^2}{2((k+1)^2 + 1)} \right] \quad (100)$$

where k denotes the inner curvature in their formulation. The definition of the Bingham number in the present work is four times that used by Roberts & Cox (2020); accordingly, their result is multiplied by a factor of four. They define the inner and outer radii of curvature of the curved slit as $1/k$ and $1 + 1/k$, respectively. Therefore, the curvature ratio κ used in the present study is related to their formulation as follows:

$$\kappa = \frac{\frac{1}{2}}{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{k}} = \frac{k}{k+2} \quad (101)$$

Rearranging (101) gives the following expression:

$$k = \frac{2\kappa}{1-\kappa} \quad (102)$$

Finally, substitution of (102) into (100) gives the critical Bingham number as a function of the curvature ratio:

$$Bi_{cr} = \frac{4}{1+\kappa^2} \quad (103)$$

To compare the present results with those of Roberts & Cox (2020), a very large aspect ratio ($L = 1 \times 10^{10}$) is considered. The results of both studies are presented in Table 5. As shown, the two solutions are in excellent agreement. For example, for $\kappa = 0.95$, the deviation between the two solutions is of the order of 10^{-10} .

Table 5. Critical Bingham number for viscoplastic flow in curved slits.

Curvature Ratio (κ)	0.01	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.95
Robert and Cox (2020)	3.9996	3.9604	3.8462	3.4483	2.9412	2.4390	2.1025
Present study	3.9996	3.9604	3.8462	3.4483	2.9412	2.4390	2.1025

For the case of a curved slit, the aspect ratio L tends to infinity. From (30b), we obtain $\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = 4/(1 + \kappa^2)$. This value coincides with the critical Bingham number reported by Roberts & Cox (2020) (Eq. (103)), as well as with the results of the present study (see Table 5). A key consequence of this result is that $\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}}$ for all values of κ , so that the condition for plug existence is satisfied only at the critical point itself. As a result, there is no admissible range of the Bingham number over which a static plug can exist. Therefore, viscoplastic flow in a curved slit does not admit a static plug under any conditions. A proof of the absence of a static plug in curved slit geometries has not been reported in the existing literature.

Figure 11 shows the evolution of static plug shapes in rectangular ducts with $L = 0.2$ for different curvature ratios. At small curvature ($\kappa = 0.01$), two separated outer plugs form near the outer-wall corners, where the local shear stress is minimal. As the curvature increases (e.g. $\kappa = 0.1$ and 0.3), the stress distribution becomes increasingly asymmetric, promoting growth of the outer plugs and their extension along the direction of curvature. Consequently, these regions approach each other and eventually merge to form a continuous outer plug. Over a wide range of curvature ratios, the outer plug boundary remains well approximated by a circular arc, indicating that the local stress field near the wall retains a quasi-uniform structure despite the imposed curvature.

Figure 12 illustrates the corresponding behavior in square ducts. In the limiting case of a straight duct ($\kappa \rightarrow 0$), the plug boundary reduces to a circular arc, consistent with classical results. As curvature increases, the outer plug expands while the inner plug shrinks, reflecting the redistribution of stresses induced by curvature. For $\kappa > 0.2$, the plug boundary departs from circular symmetry and elongates in the direction of curvature, indicating stronger geometric influence on the stress field. At sufficiently large curvature ($\kappa > 0.4$), the outer plugs merge to form a continuous region with an approximately elliptical shape, marking a clear transition in plug topology.

Figure 13 presents the results for rectangular ducts with a larger aspect ratio ($L = 5$). In this case, the outer plugs remain separated over a wider range of curvature ratios, owing to the increased geometric anisotropy of the cross-section. However, as the curvature becomes sufficiently large, these regions eventually merge. Notably, at large aspect ratios, the plug

boundaries adopt an elliptical shape at lower curvature ratios than in lower-aspect-ratio cases. This behavior highlights the combined effect of curvature and aspect ratio on the topology and morphology of static plugs.

Figure 14 presents a regime map of static plug configurations in the (κ, L) plane. Regions (I) and (II) correspond to configurations in which the outer static plugs remain separated and become connected, respectively. The boundary between these regions defines a curvature-dependent transition controlled by the aspect ratio. For small values of L , the transition occurs at very small values of κ , indicating that even weak curvature is sufficient to induce merging of the outer plugs. In contrast, for large values of L , the transition curve shifts towards $\kappa \rightarrow 1$, so that the connected-plug regime is not realized within the admissible range of curvature ratios.

In the limiting cases, the behavior of static plugs can be understood by considering the two asymptotic limits separately. First, as $L \rightarrow 0$ with $\kappa \rightarrow 0$, the geometry approaches a straight slit. In this limit case, the locations at which static plugs would form shift asymptotically towards infinity, so that no finite dead region can be sustained within the flow domain. Second, as $L \rightarrow \infty$, the duct reduces to a curved slit for any admissible curvature ratio κ . In this case, the same behavior is observed: the admissible locations for static plug formation shift to infinity, and no finite static plug region can exist within the domain. In particular, in the curved slit limit, this result is consistent with the analytical condition $\text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}} = \text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}} = 4/(1 + \kappa^2)$, which implies that there is no finite interval of Bingham numbers over which a static plug can exist.

Table 6 reports the critical Bingham number Bi_{Cr} for curved rectangular ducts over a range of curvature ratios and aspect ratios. Comparison with Table 2 shows that $\text{Bi}_{\text{Cr}} > \text{Bi}_{\text{Ex}}$ for all cases considered; hence, according to the plug-existence criterion, static plugs are admissible throughout the parameter range reported in Table 6. The variation of Bi_{Cr} reflects the geometry-dependent balance between the imposed pressure gradient and the yield stress at the cessation threshold. Since the critical condition corresponds to zero flow rate, inertial and viscous effects do not enter the determination of Bi_{Cr} ; the critical state is governed solely by the distribution of the pressure-gradient-induced stress and the yield stress. For $L < 1$, Bi_{Cr} varies non-monotonically with curvature. For example, at $L = 0.25$, Bi_{Cr} decreases from 4.1474 at $\kappa = 0.01$ to 4.0998 at $\kappa = 0.2$, and then increases sharply to 7.1496 at $\kappa = 0.9$. This behavior can be interpreted as a consequence

of curvature-induced redistribution of the stress field. At moderate curvature, the outer-wall static plugs grow and merge, as shown in Figure 11, which lowers the pressure gradient required to satisfy the critical balance. At larger curvature ratios, however, the radial weighting of the pressure-gradient term becomes increasingly dominant near the inner wall. The critical pressure gradient must then increase to maintain the balance with the yield stress over the admissible plug boundary, leading to the observed rise in Bi_{Cr} . For $L = 1$, the dependence on curvature is weaker. The critical Bingham number decreases from 4.2409 at $\kappa = 0.01$ to 3.7178 at $\kappa = 0.7$, followed by a slight increase to 3.8169 at $\kappa = 0.9$. This transitional behavior is consistent with the evolution of plug morphology shown in Figure 12, where the plug boundary gradually departs from the circular-arc shape of the straight-duct limit and becomes increasingly biased towards the outer side as curvature increases.

For $L > 1$, Bi_{Cr} decreases monotonically with increasing curvature ratio. For instance, at $L = 10$, it decreases from 4.0732 at $\kappa = 0.01$ to 2.3976 at $\kappa = 0.9$. This trend is consistent with Figure 13, where the outer plugs remain separated over a wider range of curvature ratios, and the geometry progressively approaches the curved-slit limit as L increases. In this regime, the critical condition approaches the slit-like balance $Bi_{Cr} = 4/(1 + \kappa^2)$, and the required critical pressure gradient decreases with curvature. At fixed curvature ratio, Bi_{Cr} generally decreases with increasing aspect ratio, particularly at large κ . For example, at $\kappa = 0.9$, Bi_{Cr} decreases from 7.1496 at $L = 0.25$ to 2.3976 at $L = 10$. This decrease reflects the transition from a low-aspect-ratio geometry, in which curvature strongly amplifies the weighted pressure-gradient balance, to a slit-like geometry, where the simpler curved-slit limit governs the critical condition. Thus, Table 6 shows that Bi_{Cr} is controlled by the combined effects of aspect ratio, curvature, and static-plug topology at the cessation threshold.

Figure 11. Evolution of static plug shapes in curved rectangular ducts at $L = 0.2$ with increasing curvature ratio.

Figure 12. Evolution of static plug shapes in curved square ducts with increasing curvature ratio.

Figure 13. Evolution of static plug shapes in curved rectangular ducts at $L = 5$ with increasing curvature ratio.

Figure 14. Regime map of outer static plug configurations in curved rectangular ducts at the critical condition in the (κ, L) plane.

Table 6. Critical Bingham number Bi_{Cr} in curved rectangular ducts as a function of curvature ratio (κ) and aspect ratio (L).

Curvature Ratio (κ)	Aspect Ratio (L)								
	0.25	0.5	1	1.5	2	4	6	8	10
0.01	4.1474	4.2111	4.2409	4.2302	4.2112	4.1474	4.1107	4.0882	4.0732
0.1	4.1324	4.1948	4.2221	4.2089	4.1877	4.1185	4.0791	4.0551	4.0390
0.2	4.0998	4.1460	4.1658	4.1454	4.1178	4.0336	3.9864	3.9577	3.9387
0.3	4.1506	4.0697	4.0741	4.0431	4.0068	3.8994	3.8407	3.8055	3.7821
0.4	4.2858	4.0432	3.9509	3.9071	3.8599	3.7256	3.6537	3.6108	3.5826
0.5	4.5014	4.0841	3.8224	3.7429	3.6850	3.5233	3.4381	3.3878	3.3548
0.6	4.8195	4.1898	3.7461	3.5754	3.48500	3.3031	3.2065	3.1497	3.1126
0.7	5.2759	4.3690	3.7178	3.4526	3.3090	3.0743	2.9691	2.9075	2.8676
0.8	5.9719	4.6518	3.7376	3.3697	3.1703	2.8486	2.7340	2.6698	2.6281
0.9	7.1496	5.1086	3.8169	3.3258	3.0666	2.6577	2.5156	2.4430	2.3976

6. Approximate analysis for the prediction of static plug shape

Equation (A3) provides an exact description of the interface of the static plug. Owing to its complexity, however, its application to different geometries is not straightforward. An elliptical shape is therefore considered here as a potential approximation for representing the topology of static plugs. In this section, the validity of this approximation is examined. Accordingly, the shapes of the inner and outer static plugs are approximated by the following relation:

$$y = y_c + \alpha \sqrt{\beta^2 - (x - x_c)^2} \quad (104)$$

where $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha \neq 1$ correspond to circular and elliptical shapes, respectively. The proposed approximation is examined here for rectangular ducts. In this case, one-quarter of an ellipse is fitted to the interface of the static plug. The geometric parameters x_c , y_c and β are obtained directly, while the remaining parameter, α , is determined through curve fitting. The root-mean-square (RMS) deviation between the exact interface and the fitted curve is used as the objective function, and the optimization is performed via simulated annealing. The resulting parameters for a range of aspect ratios and curvature ratios are reported in Table 7. Owing to symmetry, the values of x_c and y_c are presented only for the plugs located on the upper wall. The data in Table 7 show that the elliptical approximation provides a consistently accurate representation of the static plug interface. The RMS error typically lies in the range 10^{-4} – 10^{-2} , while the mean absolute error remains below approximately 2%. For example, for $L = 0.5$ and $\kappa = 0.1$, the RMS error is 4.94×10^{-4} , and for $L = 1$, $\kappa = 0.1$, it is 6.64×10^{-4} , both indicating an excellent agreement between the fitted ellipse and the exact interface.

The parameter α provides further insight into the shape of the plug boundary. At small curvature ratios, α remains close to unity (e.g. $\alpha = 0.9637$ for $L = 0.5$, $\kappa = 0.1$), confirming that the interface is well approximated by a circular arc. As the curvature increases, α deviates progressively from unity, indicating a transition toward an elliptical shape. This deviation becomes particularly pronounced at larger curvature ratios and aspect ratios; for instance, α reaches values as high as 2.6569 and 3.2471 for $L = 5$ and $L = 10$ at $\kappa = 0.75$, respectively.

The fitted parameter y_c also captures the topological change of the outer plugs. For cases where $y_c \neq 0$, the outer plugs remain separated, whereas $y_c = 0$ corresponds to the merging of the outer

plugs into a single continuous region. This transition is clearly reflected in Table 7; for example, at $L = 0.5$, the outer plugs are separated at $\kappa = 0.1$ ($y_c = 0.1080$) but become connected at $\kappa = 0.4$ ($y_c = 0$). The results demonstrate that the elliptical approximation captures both the geometry and topology of static plugs with high accuracy over a wide range of parameters. The systematic variation of α , together with the consistently low fitting errors, indicates that this approximation provides a robust and practical description of static plug interfaces in curved rectangular ducts.

Table 7. Fitted ellipse parameters for static plug interfaces in rectangular ducts.

Case	x_c	y_c	α	β	RMS	Mean of Error (%)
$L = 0.5$ $\kappa = 0.1$	-0.6946	0.2055	0.9637	0.3054	4.9387e-04	0.0919
	0.6167	0.1080	1.0198	0.3833	0.0011	0.2756
$L = 0.5$ $\kappa = 0.4$	-0.8093	0.3293	0.8970	0.1907	3.2472e-04	0.0620
	0.0634	0	1.1296	0.4400	0.0025	0.8636
$L = 0.5$ $\kappa = 0.75$	-0.9116	0.4284	0.8146	0.0884	3.3375e-04	0.0613
	-0.6462	0	1.3983	0.3533	0.0043	1.3862
$L = 1$ $\kappa = 0.1$	-0.5359	0.5590	0.9505	0.4641	6.6420e-04	0.0495
	0.4014	0.3769	1.0375	0.5986	0.0020	0.2184
$L = 1$ $\kappa = 0.4$	-0.7130	0.7550	0.8571	0.2870	7.2626e-04	0.0691
	0.2244	0.0464	1.2187	0.7756	0.0061	0.9131
$L = 1$ $\kappa = 0.75$	-0.8804	0.9089	0.7689	0.1196	5.8852e-04	0.0540
	-0.5974	0	1.6324	0.6036	0.0103	1.6388
$L = 5$ $\kappa = 0.1$	-0.2522	4.3072	0.9287	0.7478	0.0012	0.0178
	0.0096	3.9347	1.0700	0.9904	0.0042	0.0780
$L = 5$ $\kappa = 0.4$	-0.5804	4.6632	0.8094	0.4196	0.0016	0.0294
	-0.3308	3.0115	1.4745	1.3308	0.0183	0.3767
$L = 5$ $\kappa = 0.75$	-0.8646	4.8998	0.7469	0.1354	7.5521e-04	0.0136
	-0.6055	0.6529	2.6569	1.6055	0.0529	1.3954
$L = 10$ $\kappa = 0.1$	-0.2198	9.2792	0.9246	0.7802	0.0011	0.0083
	-0.0741	8.8363	1.0786	1.0741	0.0046	0.0415
$L = 10$ $\kappa = 0.4$	-0.5820	9.6643	0.8096	0.4180	0.0016	0.0144
	-0.4383	7.7553	1.5391	1.4383	0.0218	0.2107
$L = 10$ $\kappa = 0.75$	-0.8854	9.9118	0.7769	0.1146	5.4316e-04	0.0049
	-0.7535	4.1955	3.2471	1.7535	0.0689	0.7599

The white and grey rows correspond to the inner and outer static plug regions, respectively.

7. Optimized curved duct geometry without static plugs

As discussed previously, for curved elliptical ducts with aspect ratios in the range $0.61 < L < 1.63$, static plugs are negligible at small curvature ratios, since Bi_{Ex} is approximately equal to Bi_{Cr} to four decimal places. This behavior corresponds to region I in Figure 9, where the static plug is either absent or confined to a negligible size. It has also been shown that static plugs do not exist in curved slit geometries. These observations suggest that the presence of static plugs is strongly dependent on the interplay between geometry and curvature. This naturally raises the question of whether a cross-sectional geometry can be designed such that static plugs are entirely eliminated. The identification of such static-plug-free regimes has direct implications for preventing flow arrest in curved conduits, such as blood vessels with pathological curvature or vascular grafts. Designing cross-sections that inherently suppress stagnant regions could reduce the risk of thrombus formation and improve the long-term patency of implanted devices.

In this section, the existence of an optimized cross-section without static plugs is investigated. In other words, we seek a geometry whose wall shape coincides with the static plug boundary at the critical condition. Such a configuration can be obtained by constructing a closed curve from the solution to (42).

Suppose that the lower half of the cross-section is traced counterclockwise starting from $x = x_0 = -1$; it must then terminate at $x = x_1 \leq 1$. Owing to symmetry, $c_2 = 0$, and the remaining parameters c_1 , λ and x_1 can be determined by imposing a root condition at $x = x_1$ and singularities at $x = x_0 = -1$ and $x = x_1$:

$$\begin{cases} \text{at } x = -1: dy/dx \rightarrow \infty \text{ or } dx/dy = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda^2(1-\kappa)^4 - (\kappa/2 - 1 + c_1)^2 = 0 \\ \text{at } x = x_1: dy/dx \rightarrow \infty \text{ or } dx/dy = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda^2(1+\kappa x_1)^4 - (\kappa x_1^2/2 + x_1 + c_1)^2 = 0 \\ \text{at } x = x_1: y = 0 \end{cases} \quad (105)$$

From the first two equations in (105), expressions for λ and c_1 are obtained in terms of κ and x_1 :

$$\lambda = \frac{\kappa x_1^2/2 + x_1 - \kappa/2 + 1}{\kappa^2 x_1^2 + \kappa^2 + 2\kappa x_1 - 2\kappa + 2} \quad (106a)$$

$$c_1 = -\frac{\kappa^3 x_1^2 - 2\kappa^2 x_1^2 + 2\kappa^2 x_1 + \kappa x_1^2 / 2 - 4\kappa x_1 + \kappa / 2 + x_1 - 1}{\kappa^2 x_1^2 + \kappa^2 + 2\kappa x_1 - 2\kappa + 2} \quad (106b)$$

Therefore, the only remaining unknown is x_1 , which must be determined from the closure condition $y(x_1) = 0$, with $x_1 \neq x_0$. Figure 15 shows the solutions of (42) for $\kappa = 0.2$ and several values of x_1 . All curves originate from the common point $x = x_0 = -1$, where $y = 0$, and exhibit vertical tangents at both $x = x_0$ and $x = x_1$.

For a closed and symmetric cross-section to be obtained, the curve must return to the x -axis at $x = x_1$, i.e. $y(x_1) = 0$. However, Figure 15 shows that this condition is not satisfied for any non-trivial value of x_1 . Instead, the endpoint value remains strictly positive, $y(x_1) > 0$, for all $x_1 > x_0$. This behavior is highlighted by the red dashed curve representing the locus of $y(x_1)$, which increases monotonically as x_1 approaches 1. Consequently, the solution of (42) does not yield a closed curve and $y(x)$ is always an open curve for $\kappa > 0$. In contrast, in the limiting case $\kappa = 0$, the curvature-induced asymmetry vanishes, and the solution reduces to a circular profile, which forms a closed curve.

Figure 15. Solutions of (42) for $\kappa = 0.2$ and different values of x_1 . The red dashed curve shows the locus of the endpoint values $y(x_1)$.

Now, we seek cross-sectional shapes in which a substantial portion of the wall is constructed using the solution to (42), extending from the inner side towards the outer side of the curvature. Such shapes are not unique, and the aim here is to construct representative examples that may suppress the formation of static plugs even at the critical condition.

In curved ducts with smooth boundaries and no sharp corners, static plugs tend to form preferentially near the outer wall. Motivated by this observation, a family of open curves is generated from (42) by initiating the solution at $x = x_0 = -1$ (inner wall) and extending it toward the outer region. As shown in Figure 16, these curves correspond to different curvature ratios and remain open for all $\kappa > 0$. To construct a closed cross-section, the open curve obtained from (42) is combined with a straight segment representing the inner wall (shown in red). The starting and ending points of the open curves are indicated by filled and open circles, respectively. The constant c_2 is selected such that the resulting configuration satisfies the symmetry condition and ensures a smooth transition between the curve and the inner wall.

For the straight-duct case ($\kappa = 0$), the solution of (42) naturally yields a closed circular profile. However, for non-zero curvature ratios, the open nature of the solution reflects the curvature-induced asymmetry, which prevents the curve from closing. Despite this, the combined construction shown in Figure 16 produces well-defined closed cross-sections. Importantly, for all geometries illustrated in Figure 16, no static plug is formed along the walls at the corresponding curvature ratios. This demonstrates that, although the solution of (42) alone does not yield a closed boundary for $\kappa > 0$, it can still serve as a guiding interface for designing plug-free curved duct geometries when complemented by an appropriate geometric closure at the inner wall.

Figure 16. Constructed cross-sections for different κ based on (42), showing plug-free configurations.

8. Conclusions

In this study, the existence and topology of static plugs, together with the critical condition for viscoplastic flow in curved ducts, have been investigated within a unified analytical and computational framework. By invoking the law of conservation of angular momentum, a general existence criterion has been established for stagnant regions in curved geometries with arbitrary cross-sections. An exact parametric formulation has been derived to describe the interface of dead

regions at the critical condition, and the corresponding critical Bingham numbers and topology parameters have been determined using a simulated annealing approach.

The formulation is further recast in a variational setting, in which a curvature-weighted perimeter-to-area ratio governs the critical condition. This leads to the formulation of a new theorem—the weighted Cheeger-type criterion for plug formation in curved ducts—which provides a unifying theoretical framework for the problem. Within this framework, a criterion for the existence of static plug regions is derived, and plug-free regimes are explicitly identified for specific classes of geometries. The theorem thus offers a consistent interpretation of plug formation and elucidates the geometric constraints that determine the admissible static plug regions. As a direct application of this theorem, for curved elliptical ducts, the analytical solution (B8), derived from equations (86)–(88), enables precise identification of plug-free regions (see figure 9). For the special case of circular curved pipes ($L = 1$), a critical curvature ratio is identified, below which ($\kappa < 0.382$) no static plugs exist at the cessation threshold. In the limiting case of curved slits, this condition is satisfied for all curvature ratios, implying that static plug formation is entirely suppressed. The results further indicate that, outside the identified plug-free regimes, static plugs persist in curved elliptical duct geometries at moderate to large curvature ratios. These findings have direct practical implications for biomedical engineering. The curvature and aspect-ratio conditions that eliminate static plugs, established here for the first time, can guide the design of vascular grafts, stents, and bypass conduits intended for tortuous arterial paths. By tailoring the cross-sectional shape to remain within the plug-free regime (e.g., circular curved vessels with $\kappa < 0.382$), it may be possible to reduce the risk of flow arrest, thrombosis, and occlusion in curved blood vessels. Furthermore, in the context of foam sclerotherapy for varicose veins, where a yield-stress foam is injected to displace blood, the present criteria suggest that veins or injection channels designed with plug-free geometries could prevent the formation of static foam zones that compromise displacement efficacy. Thus, the proposed weighted Cheeger-type criterion not only advances the fundamental understanding of viscoplastic flow in curved ducts but also offers, based on the specific results of this study (including the constructed plug-free cross-sections of Section 7), a rational basis for developing medical devices and treatments that minimize pathological flow cessation.

For rectangular and elliptical ducts, the topology of stagnant regions exhibits multiple regimes depending on the aspect ratio and curvature ratio, as summarized in the regime maps. In rectangular ducts with $L < 1$, the critical Bingham number initially decreases with increasing curvature and then increases at higher curvature ratios, whereas for $L > 1$, it decreases monotonically with curvature. At fixed curvature, the critical Bingham number also decreases with increasing aspect ratio.

Despite the complexity of the exact plug boundaries, it is shown that their topology can be accurately approximated by elliptical shapes, with errors typically below 2%. Furthermore, the analytical solution for the plug interface yields open curves for non-zero curvature ratios, indicating that a closed cross-section cannot be constructed directly from this interface. Nevertheless, the analytical identification of plug-free regions, together with the construction of approximate plug geometries, provides useful guidelines for the design of curved ducts with reduced or suppressed stagnant regions.

Appendix-A

This appendix presents an exact formulation for the topology of static plug interfaces in curved ducts. The following change of variables is introduced to evaluate the integral in (42):

$$\varrho = 1 + \kappa x \tag{A1}$$

Substituting (A1) into (42) yields:

$$y' = \pm \frac{\frac{\varrho^2 - 1}{2\kappa} + c_1}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 \varrho^4 - \left(\frac{\varrho^2 - 1}{2\kappa} + c_1\right)^2}} \xrightarrow{\text{Integration}} y = \pm [f(\varrho) - f(\varrho_0)] - c_2 \tag{A2}$$

The result of the integral in (A2), $f(\varrho)$, is given by:

$$f(\varrho) = \frac{1}{\kappa\phi_2} \sqrt{\frac{(\phi_3 - \varrho^2\phi_1)(\phi_3 - \varrho^2\phi_2)}{\phi_1\phi_3(2\varrho^2\phi_3 - \varrho^4\phi_1\phi_2 - \phi_3^2)}} \left[2\kappa\lambda\phi_3 F\left(\varrho\sqrt{\frac{\phi_1}{\phi_3}}, \sqrt{\frac{\phi_2}{\phi_1}}\right) - \phi_3 E\left(\varrho\sqrt{\frac{\phi_1}{\phi_3}}, \sqrt{\frac{\phi_2}{\phi_1}}\right) \right] \quad (\text{A3})$$

where $\phi_1 = 1 + 2\kappa\lambda$, $\phi_2 = 1 - 2\kappa\lambda$, and $\phi_3 = 1 - 2\kappa c_1$, and; $F(\phi, k)$ and $E(\phi, k)$ denote the incomplete elliptic integrals of the first and second kind, respectively, defined as:

$$F(\phi, k) = \int_0^\phi \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta}} \quad (\text{A4a})$$

$$E(\phi, k) = \int_0^\phi \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (\text{A4b})$$

Appendix B. Details of determining κ_c for curved elliptical ducts

Expanding $Q_L(\kappa)$ in (85) and using the symmetry of the elliptical cross-section gives

$$Q_L(\kappa) = Q_L^{(0)} + \kappa^2 Q_L^{(2)} \quad (\text{B1})$$

where

$$Q_L^{(0)} = \frac{1}{\pi L} \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{\sin^2 \phi + L^2 \cos^2 \phi} d\phi \quad (\text{B2a})$$

and

$$Q_L^{(2)} = \frac{1}{\pi L} \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 \phi \sqrt{\sin^2 \phi + L^2 \cos^2 \phi} d\phi \quad (\text{Bab})$$

Using standard reductions, the coefficients are obtained as follows. For $0 < L < 1$,

$$Q_L^{(0)} = \frac{4}{\pi L} E(1 - L^2), \quad Q_L^{(2)} = \frac{4}{3\pi L(1 - L^2)} \left[(1 - 2L^2)E(1 - L^2) + L^2 K(1 - L^2) \right] \quad (\text{B3a})$$

For $L > 1$,

$$Q_L^{(0)} = \frac{4}{\pi} E\left(1 - \frac{1}{L^2}\right), \quad Q_L^{(2)} = \frac{4}{3\pi\left(1 - \frac{1}{L^2}\right)} \left[\left(2 - \frac{1}{L^2}\right) E\left(1 - \frac{1}{L^2}\right) - \frac{1}{L^2} K\left(1 - \frac{1}{L^2}\right) \right] \quad (\text{B3b})$$

where $K(k)$ and $E(k)$ denote the complete elliptic integrals of the first and second kind, respectively, defined as

$$K(k) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta}} \quad (\text{B4a})$$

$$E(k) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (\text{B4b})$$

The maximum of $F_L(t, \kappa)$ is obtained by writing $u = \cos t$ from (86). Then

$$F_L(u, \kappa) = L \frac{1 + \kappa u \left[3 + 2(L^2 - 1)u^2 \right]}{\left[1 + (L^2 - 1)u^2 \right]^{3/2}}, \quad -1 \leq u \leq 1 \quad (\text{B5})$$

The stationary point satisfies:

$$u_* = \frac{\kappa}{L^2 - 1} \quad (\text{B6})$$

For $0 < L < 1$, the maximum occurs at the endpoint $u = 1$, giving

$$\max F_L = \frac{1}{L^2} + \kappa \left(2 + \frac{1}{L^2} \right) \quad (\text{B7a})$$

For $L > 1$, two branches must be considered. The endpoint branch gives

$$\max F_L = \frac{1}{L^2} + \kappa \left(2 + \frac{1}{L^2} \right) \quad (\text{B7b})$$

whereas the interior branch, valid only when $0 \leq \kappa \leq L^2 - 1$, gives

$$\max F_L = L \frac{(L^2 - 1) + 2\kappa^2}{\sqrt{(L^2 - 1) \left[(L^2 - 1) + \kappa^2 \right]}} \quad (\text{B7c})$$

Substituting (B1) and (B7) into the onset condition

$$Q_L(\kappa_c) = \max F_L$$

yields the algebraic equations for the critical curvature ratio. For the endpoint branch, applicable to $0 < L < 1$ and also to the endpoint branch for $L > 1$,

$$Q_L^{(2)} \kappa_c^2 - \left(2 + \frac{1}{L^2}\right) \kappa_c + \left(Q_L^{(0)} - \frac{1}{L^2}\right) = 0 \quad (\text{B8a})$$

For the interior branch, possible only for $L > 1$, the critical curvature ratio satisfies

$$\left(Q_L^{(0)} + \kappa_c^2 Q_L^{(2)}\right)^2 (L^2 - 1) \left[(L^2 - 1) + \kappa_c^2\right] = L^2 \left[(L^2 - 1) + 2\kappa_c^2\right]^2 \quad (\text{B8b})$$

The physically relevant value of κ_c is the smallest admissible root obtained from (B8a) or (B8b), satisfying

$$0 \leq \kappa_c < 1 \quad (\text{B9})$$

with the additional restriction

$$0 \leq \kappa_c \leq L^2 - 1 \quad (\text{B10})$$

for the interior branch.

Availability of data and materials

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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